

Scheme 1

Bis-(1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-5-thiol (2): It was prepared by cyclisation of 1 with carbon disulphide in alkaline medium⁸.

Bis-(1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-5-hydrazine (3)⁸: To bis-(1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-5-thiol (0.1 mol) dissolved in ethanol (99%) was added hydrazine hydrate (99%, 0.2 mol) and the mixture refluxed for 6 h. Excess solvent was then distilled off. The resulting solid separated out on cooling was filtered and recrystallised (68%), m.p. 193° (Found : N, 56.56. C₄H₈N₈O₂ requires : 56.80%).

Bis-(1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-5-aryldiazones (4): A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%; 15–20 ml) and appropriate aldehyde (0.02 mol) was refluxed on a water-bath at 80° for 4 h. The product was isolated and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE HYDRAZONES (4)^a

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₂	118	57
2.	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₈ O ₄	170	54
3.	3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₈ O ₄	151	58
4.	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₈ O ₄	163	61
5.	4-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ N ₈ O ₂	146	58
6.	2-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₈ O ₄	149	55
7.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₈ O ₄	178	59
8.	3-OCH ₃ -4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₆	177	56
9.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₆	209	55
10.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ N ₈ O ₆	184	56
11.	3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₄ H ₈ N ₈ O ₆	162	57
12.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₈ O ₂	148	62
13.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₈ O ₂	121	59
14.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₁₀ O ₂	158	60
15.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₁₀ O ₂	167	54

^aAll compounds showed satisfactory N analysis.

Pharmacological screening: The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against

S. aureus and *E. coli*. Representative compounds were screened for antitubercular activity against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R_v).

Results and Discussion

Out of 15 compounds, 6 compounds were found to be active (zone of inhibition > 20 mm) against gram +ve bacteria *S. aureus* and 7 compounds active against gram -ve bacteria *E. coli*, and 3 compounds were active against both the species. Compounds having 4-methyl, 3,4-methylenedioxy and 3-methoxy-4-hydroxy substitutions were found to be active against both the species.

Out of seven compounds (Table 1, sl. nos. 1, 2, 5, 6, 9, 13 and 15) screened for antitubercular activity, none was found effective at lower concentration (35 µg ml⁻¹). Compounds having phenyl, 4-methyl and 4-nitro substitution were found to be active at higher concentration (100 µg ml⁻¹).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Bhavnagar University for facilities, to the Ministry of Higher Education, Government of Gujarat, for research scholarship to one of them (M.K.J.) and to Dr. S. B. Trivedi, Director, Tuberculosis Research Centre, Amargadh, for biological screening.

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Synthesis of 2-(3'-Methylpyrazol-5-one-1'-yl)-4-arylthiazoles

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Manuscript received 8 June 1988, accepted 2 February 1989

HETEROCYCLIC compounds containing pyrazolone¹ or thiazole² moiety are known to exhibit potent fungicidal activity and as a result of which the present study based on the synthesis of some new compounds having a pyrazolone ring through

its N¹-atom linked to a thiazole nucleus at position-2 has been reported. 2-(3'-Methylpyrazol-5-one-1'-yl)-4-arylthiazoles (**1**) were synthesised from the reaction of 3-methyl-1-thiocarbamylpyrazol-5-one with α -haloketones. 3-Methyl-1-thiocarbamylpyrazol-5-one was obtained by cyclisation of thiosemicarbazone of ethylacetoacetate in ammoniacal methanol.

1a, R=H
1b, R=Cl
1c, R=Br

The structural assignments of **1a-c** were based on their element analysis and spectral data. Though the ir spectra did not display any carbonyl band, a broad band at 3400 cm⁻¹ (enolic OH) was noted, whilst the pmr spectra in addition to a broad multiplets at δ 7.2-8.2 (aromatic, thiazole ring proton and pyrazole-4 proton) revealed a singlet of one-proton intensity at δ 5.2 attributable to the enolic hydroxyl proton and also a singlet of three-proton intensity at δ 2.2 ascribed to the methyl proton at position-3. Absence of methylene signal support the enolic structure. The enolic structure strongly supported by mass spectra was due to an initial fragmentation of pyrazolone ring with sequential expulsion of N₂ and CO thereby resulted in the formation of an intense ion at *m/z* 41. However, Desmarchelier and Johns⁴ observed that the initial loss of .N₂H or .N₂R followed by a rapid loss of CO was a cause of major fragmentation in case of pyrazolone having enolic structure. These compounds (**1a-c**) are under active screening for pharmacological activities.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected.

3-Methyl-1-thiocarbamylpyrazol-5-one: Thiosemicarbazone of ethylacetoacetate (5 g) was dissolved in ammoniacal methanol (1 ml of ammonia in 9 ml of methanol) and allowed to stand for 0.5 h. The product obtained was crystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 180° (lit.⁴ 180°).

2-(3'-Methylpyrazol-5-one-1'-yl)-4-phenylthiazole (1a): A mixture of 3-methyl-1-thiocarbamylpyrazol-5-one (1.57 g, 0.01 mol) and phenacyl bromide (1.99 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (60 ml) was refluxed

for 2 h. The resulting solid was made alkaline with ammonium hydroxide, filtered, washed and crystallised from acetic acid to yield colourless crystals (**1a**; 61%), m.p. 191° (Found: C, 60.5; H, 4.0; N, 16.2; S, 12.3. C₁₃H₁₁ON₂S requires: C, 60.7; H, 4.3; N, 16.3; S, 12.5%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3400, 3040, 1610, 1540, 1510, 1480, 1410, 980 and 700 cm⁻¹; δ (TMS; CDCl₃+DMSO-d₆) 2.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.22 (1H, s, OH) and 7.2-8.2 (7H, m, ArH, thiazole and pyrazole-4 protons); *M*⁺ 258 (100%), 160 (4%), 134 (10%), 102 (11%), 69 (4%) and 41 (4.3%); **1b** (60%), m.p. 208°; **1c** (51%), m.p. 193°.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Fellowship to one of them (R.H.).

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Synthesis and Characterisation of Salicylic Acid-Dithiobiuret-Trioxane Resin†

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Manuscript received 21 July 1987, revised 22 February 1988, accepted 1 February 1989

In recent years, considerable attention has been focussed on the synthesis and the study of organic polymers which behave like amorphous semi-conductors. In this communication, we report the synthesis and characterisation of salicylic acid-dithiobiuret-trioxane (SDT) resins.

Experimental

The SDT resins were prepared by condensing salicylic acid (S) and dithiobiuret (D) with trioxane (T) in the mole ratio of 1 : 1 : 2, 2 : 1 : 3 and 3 : 1 : 4, respectively, in presence of 2 M HCl. The mixture was heated at 130 ± 2° in an oil-bath for 4 h¹. The resulting polymeric resin was washed with hot water and then with ether to remove the unreacted monomers. It was purified by dissolving in 8%

† Part of the paper presented at the 23rd. Annual Convention of Chemists, Annamalainagar, 1986.